

электронное периодическое издание

ЭКОНОМИКА

и

социум

ISSN 2225-1545

№3(118)-2024

ЭЛЕКТРОННОЕ НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКОЕ
ПЕРИОДИЧЕСКОЕ ИЗДАНИЕ

«Экономика и социум»

iupr.ru

УДК 004.02:004.5:004.9

ББК 73+65.9+60.5

ISSN 2225-1545

Свидетельство о регистрации
средства массовой коммуникации
Эл № ФС77 - 45777 от 07 июля 2011г.
Эл № ФС77 - 80454 от 01 марта 2021г.

Журнал включен в систему НЭБ (e-library) [№ 594-09/2013 от 26.09.2013](#)

Тематика журнала: актуальные вопросы современной экономики и социологии - от теоретических и экспериментальных исследований до непосредственных результатов управленческой и производственной деятельности. Публикации в журнале учитываются как опубликованные работы при защите диссертаций на соискание ученых степеней России и зарубежья.

РАЗДЕЛЫ НОМЕРА:

- Основной раздел: социально-экономические аспекты развития современного государства;
- Современные технологии управления организацией;
- Актуальные вопросы политики и права;
- Современные науки и образование;
- Информационные и коммуникативные технологии;
- Здравоохранение в обществе.

Выпуск №3(118) 2 (март, 2024). Сайт: <http://www.iupr.ru>

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THE ROLE OF COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE AND FORMING THEIR LINGUISTIC PERSONALITY

Abstract. The research examines the specifics of cognitive linguistics regarding developing communicative competence and forming students' linguistic personalities. Attention is paid to the essence of cognitive linguistics, the history of the emergence of this direction, and the current state of research. The article analyzes the ways, methods, and forms of cognitive linguistics application in the educational process to form the student's linguistic personality and develop communicative competence.

Keywords: cognitive linguistics, communicative competence, thinking, language personality, student, phenomenon.

Currently, the issues of students' linguistic personality and their communicative competence are among the key factors in organizing the educational process in higher education institutions. It is mainly driven by the fact that modern professionals should be versatile and possess a significant amount of knowledge in various fields to fulfill their professional duties. Moreover, they should be able to communicate with different interlocutors and use language units correctly during real-life interactions. Consequently, applying an approach that enables the rapid and effective formation of students' linguistic personalities becomes essential. Given the relevance of this topic, the question arises about using cognitive linguistics in the educational process in higher education institutions to shape students' linguistic personalities and develop communicative competence. An innovative approach to forming a linguistic personality also needs to be considered.

At the present stage, considerable attention is given to studying cognitive linguistics. It is caused by the relatively recent emergence of this concept, the study of cognitive linguistics in the educational process of linguistic fields, and the availability of only a few of these concepts. Consequently, there is no unified understanding of "cognitive linguistics," leading to the development of various conceptualizations of this phenomenon. In general, "cognitive linguistics" is an interdisciplinary science exploring cognitive processes in human consciousness. It facilitates thinking and understanding of the surrounding world. Cognitive linguistics, also known as cognitology, investigates models of consciousness related to cognitive processes such as acquiring, generating, utilizing, storing, and transmitting knowledge and processing and transforming information obtained through various means. It also involves decision-making based on this

information, understanding human language, constructing logical inferences, argumentation, and other forms of cognitive activities.

The history of this field is relatively brief. Cognitive linguistics emerged in the second half of the 1970s in the United States. This research field intersects with several disciplines as it integrates the efforts of scholars from various domains such as psychology, philosophy, logic, linguistics, psycholinguistics, anthropology, mathematics, cybernetics, and others. A significant milestone in the development of this science was the establishment of the International Cognitive Linguistics Association during the symposium in 1989 organized by René Dirven. Thus, it can be asserted that cognitive linguistics is a contemporary direction with a history of only about half a century. The basis of cognitive linguistics is the assertion that language is at the center of all human mental activity, representing its cognitive processes and abilities. It provides access to the world of others and their consciousness structures. At the present stage of the development of linguistic research, the solution of many theoretical and practical problems is associated with the study of the specifics of knowledge representation in language. In other words, there is a relationship between cognitive and linguistic structures, which led to the separation of cognitive science as a separate field. As a branch of linguistics, cognitive linguistics studies the functioning of language as a kind of cognitive (gnostic) activity and the cognitive mechanisms and structures of the human psyche through linguistic phenomena. The object of cognitive linguistics is cognition in its linguistic reflection. Cognition refers to the set of mental structures and processes that encompass all human cognitive activity. The subject of its study includes models of knowledge and human conceptions of the surrounding world, such as worldviews, frames, stereotypes, archetypes, concepts, and the ways of their verbalization. Cognitive linguistics aims to describe the dependence and correlation between the structures of language and human consciousness. Based on the peculiarities of this dependence, cognitive linguists seek to explain how the world and the human being are structured, what causes certain physical, physiological, and psychological phenomena and processes, and what their consequences are. In other words, it refers to the ability to communicate effectively in various contexts. This competence is vital in learning a foreign language, as it involves practical adherence to the principles and basics of using a particular language system in a specific situation. Regarding communicative competence, cognitive linguistics aims to develop the following types of students' thinking. The first type is professional thinking, which involves the ability of students to apply acquired knowledge in practical situations after completing their educational institution. If a task exceeds their experience, they should be able to compare different phenomena and establish connections based on their differences and similarities, thereby facilitating problem-solving. It is essential as modern graduates in foreign language faculties often work with political, cinematographic, musical, and narrative texts that contain numerous neologisms and metaphors. Therefore,

professionals must be able to identify similarities between concepts and grasp the essence of specific expressions by understanding the formation of new connections or collocations. The second type is abstract thinking, wherein students should identify connections and determine the relationships between intangible things. Such texts are often found in political discourse or advertising. Understanding the origin of these expressions allows for a clear comprehension of the formation of specific mechanisms. The third type is systems thinking, which involves sequential and logical reasoning, organizing relationships between different phenomena in students' consciousness. The development of systems thinking is essential when working with scientific and technical texts. A specialist must offer the target audience a global understanding of a particular phenomenon by reproducing the cause-and-effect relationship, predicting further developments, and reproducing the impact of one direction on another. The fourth type is critical thinking, characterized by the ability to evaluate phenomena objectively, their relationships with other processes, and their similarities and differences. This type of thinking is essential when working with scientific, technical, and political texts. The specialists must present something that immediately demonstrates the essence of things without indicating the specialist's bias.

During the study, the authors found that cognitive linguistics is a field of philology that involves exploring language through the analysis of human consciousness. The article revealed the role of cognitive linguistics in developing communicative competence and forming students' linguistic personalities. The authors emphasized the practical value of cognitive linguistics. The essence of the concept of "cognitive linguistics" was elucidated in the article. The importance of cognitive linguistics for the development of modern linguistics was justified. It was found that cognitive linguistics is a new direction in linguistics that reflects the connection between language, thought, and culture. This direction has a long history, contributing to its research relevance. Various types of thinking, such as abstract, professional, critical, fast, and systemic thinking, were identified as being formed through applying cognitive linguistics in the educational process. The authors also described the main characteristics of this direction. The practical value of cognitive linguistics in developing students' communicative competence was revealed. It was established that the practical value of cognitive linguistics lies in developing new forms of thinking in students and their communicative realization in the linguistic environment. Accordingly, the principles of cognitive linguistics used in organizing the educational process are anthropocentrism, cognitivism, expansionism, and explanativeness. Special attention was given to the case method as a key methodology of cognitive linguistics implemented in the educational sphere. The article characterized the methods of forming students' communicative competence by applying cognitive linguistics. It was emphasized that cognitive linguistics is realized primarily through the student's life experience and the correlation of various subject areas and through the establishment of

differences between different phenomena. It was determined that the awareness of different types of thinking occurs through the student's cognition and self-discovery. The mechanisms of applying cognitive linguistics in forming students' linguistic personalities were described. The linguistic personality of the student is realized through a detailed assimilation of the structure of the concept. The main types of concepts used in the speech were identified. It was determined that the components of the concept significantly influence its perception and are multilevel. All of this allows for a clearer perception of the linguistic picture of the world and the formation of the student's linguistic personality.

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